

Paper 11

ROLE OF ELECTRONICS IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY – CLOTHING, DESIGN PRODUCTS AND PRODUCTION

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Email: itzamjad@gmail.com**Abstract**

Textile industry is one of the ancient industries which came into existence along with the mankind. As we all know that during the beginning of Middle Ages humans used to spin and weave cotton using needle and thread. This industry took a giant leap during the industrial revolution during last century and changed the way of spinning and weaving cloths. But these changes remain steady for more than a century until it became a subject for scientific study or need for designing the machines that can complete the complicated tasks of cloth spinning, fabric designing, production etc. automatically and more efficiently. The latest developments in the field of Electronics made it possible to achieve greater efficiency through the electronics machines. Today's textile industry is focusing on implementing these latest technologies in all the sectors of textile industry to increase the efficient production at lesser prices.

Keywords: Textile industry, Electronics, complicated tasks, fabric designs, latest technologies, Electronics machines.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Textile Industry consists of design, production and distribution of cloth and clothing using raw materials. The textile industry in India has been a pioneer industry. Industrialization in other fields has mainly been achieved on the back of the resource generation by the textile industry [1]. The raw materials may be natural or synthetic. The natural raw materials are obtained from sheep, goat, rabbit, silk-worm etc. or from plants. The synthetic raw materials are obtained from extruding a polymer. The archaeological surveys and studies have found that the people of Harappa civilization knew weaving and the spinning of cotton four thousand years ago. There was a drastic growth in textile technology especially in spinning and weaving of cotton. Even though the application of electronics in textile is limited but there are few interesting and useful applications of electronics in textiles. These applications are divided into seven areas as [2]

- a). Testing instruments
- b). Temperature instruments
- c). Process control
- d). Speed control
- e). Research application
- f). Programmed process control

g). Data logging

2. OBJECTIVES

- Role of electronics in testing instruments
- Electronics temperature instruments used in textile industry
- Programmed process control in textile industry
- Data logging for textile industry
- Research application
- Future applications in textile industry.
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3. ROLE OF ELECTRONICS IN TESTING INSTRUMENTS

The textile process has to deal with large number of fibers. We need to monitor continuously the condition of fiber at each stage. Achieving this manually will be highly impossible. In order to complete this task, samples are taken at different stages such as fiber, yarn, fabric and other intermediate stages to get the idea of the quality of material and the processing. Electronics instruments are used for such measurements. For example in cotton spinning by knowing the distribution of length, it is possible to guess how well the cotton will spin. Some physical methods are used to determine the length distribution but it is a time consuming and tedious job. So electronics instruments are used for measuring length distribution. Fibro graph and Atira fiber length [2] tester are the example of electronics instruments.

5. ELECTRONICS TEMPERATURE INSTRUMENTS USED IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY

Measurement of temperature is important factor to measure in textile industry. For example dye bath temperatures, fabric temperature, cylinder and hot air temperature. Temperature of these sections has to be monitored at regular intervals. Electronics thermocouples or thermistors are mostly employed to achieve this task. These thermocouples, thermistors are included in electronics circuits because thermocouples require the signals to be amplified and the resistance elements which will appear in the bridge circuits require the balancing of circuits. Infrared, non-contact thermometers are ideal for measuring temperatures of moving webs of textiles or paper. Accuracy is far better in determining actual product temperature than rolling thermocouples or oven air thermometers. Fig 1 shows a comparison of the three types of measurement.[3]

A variety of configurations for IR sensors have been developed during the past thirty years. Fixed-mount transducer, Fix-mount two-piece system, hand-held thermometers are some of the common temperature measuring instruments used in textile industries.

6. PROGRAMMED PROCESS CONTROL IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY

The textile processing machines have greater importance in textile industry. Production of qualitative and quantitative product using technically developed features increases the trading of textile. Textile manufacturing process control using electronics has the following advantages

- a. It controls the process control parameters
- b. The chances of machine breakdown are reduced.
- c. Quality and productivity of the processing material will be increased.

The Programming Logic Controller (PLC) is applied in processing machinery by using controller which is interrelated with other individual parameters. For example, If the Colour dye solution level in the tray of color dye padder is reduced, it is sensed by the pressure transducer which activates the dosing pump of the colour dye due to which the colour dye level is maintained and the chances of colour variations in the cloth reduces.

The digital controllers used in textile machineries are:[4]

1. Solenoid valves
2. Load cell
3. Thermo couple
4. Pressure/ capacitive transducers
5. Flame detectors/ photo cells
6. Moisture measuring device
7. Electrodes
8. Optical density measuring device
9. Strain gauge
10. Baume measuring device

The production speed of the machine can be increased with the help of PLC programming, automation and electronic controlling system.

The functioning of processing controllers by PLC programming system is as follows

HMI panel ↔ PLC Programmer ↔ machine transmitter

The logical diagram for correlating the individual parameter by PLC programming is as shown in fig2.

1. The load cell attached to tensioning roller measure tension over a fabric and changes the frequency of drive of pulling.
2. The thermo couple shown in fig3 is installed in drying unit to measure processing temperature which controls the temperature.
3. Washing unit consists of a pressure transducer which measure water level and activates the water pump to achieve the required water level.
4. The Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT) is used to identify irregularity in the yarn. Fig4
5. The Baume measuring device is used to measure the density of caustic liquor and changes the changes in washing parameters are made.[5]

6. Photo cells are used in weft straightener for measuring skew and bowing effect throughout the width of fabric.

Most of the textile manufacturing industries like benninger, kuster, monforts have inbuilt the electronically controlling system in machineries due to which the minimum breakdown in machineries & high productivity is possible.

The maintenance of these digital electronic controllers is also important for their efficient working, otherwise the process defect observed.

7. DATA LOGGING FOR TEXTILE INDUSTRY

The main goal of today's textile industry is to achieve maximum efficiency with high production so that a system comes into picture for achieving optimum quality and maximum production with certain features and configuration. Electronics data logging system fulfills these requirements.

"Data logging system" is an "Automated Information System" which will give you better control over production monitoring and take corrective steps immediately. Data logging system helps us to have better control over quality and production of the textile so that it will improve the "productivity" of the organization. The key to a profitable and successful weaving shed is the management of the shed to ensure it is achieving maximum efficiency. Productivity is assured by the continuous Performance of every single loom in the Mill. Unwanted stoppages Spanner in the works and drastically Impact production schedules.[7]

8. FUTURE APPLICATIONS IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY

- Electronics field may be integrated into textiles industry in future. These will have a drastic change in traditional textile applications. It may lead to new findings in many traditional textile applications. Textiles will be developed for entertainment, communication, health & safety. The researchers may be able to integrate multiple electronic devices directly into textile cloths. The dress products will increase the mobility, comfort & convenience of such device.
- A new field called e-textile is emerging which produces electronics textiles that have electronics and interconnections woven into them. Electronics Components and interconnections woven into them. Components and interconnections are a part of the fabric and thus are much less visible.
- Communicating dress: Communicating dress will be the future trends in textile industry where in the dress will be able to communication with each other and exchange messages. IR trans receiver technology will be used for this application. [7]

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